

Effect of Jig - Saw and Team - Teaching Strategies on Achievement and Retention in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

S. A. Abdulkadir¹, D. I. Wushishi¹, A. M. Chado¹, & M. Ndamitso²

Email: Suleimanabdul1999@gmail.com

Tel: 08037515086

¹Department of Science Education, Federal University of Technology, Minna Niger State

²Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Technology, Minna Niger State

Abstract

This study investigated the effects of jig - saw and team - teaching strategies on chemistry achievement and retention among secondary school students in Ilorin west local government, kwara state. The study employed quasi experimental research design using pretest posttest non randomized non control group design. Population of study consists of all Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) chemistry students in Ilorin west Kwara State. The sample size of 210 (117 male & 93 female) chemistry students using an intact class of 3 out of 10 government secondary schools were randomly selected by lottery technique in Ilorin west local government. The instruments used for data collection was Chemistry Students Achievement Test (CSAT). The CSAT was validated by experts from University of Ilorin, Ilorin kwara State. Thus, the CSAT gave a reliability Coefficient of 0.933 using Guttman Split half reliability test. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions raised and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. Findings from this study revealed that there was a significant difference between achievement of students taught chemistry using jigsaw strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method. Based on research findings for this study, it was recommended that students should be exposed to jig-saw instructional strategies frequently during Chemistry instructions so as to aid better achievement and retention in Chemistry among secondary school students.

Keyword: Jig-saw, Team teaching, chemistry achievement and retention.

Introduction

Science education is a field of study which involves producing a scientifically enlightened individual in the area of science and technology development. The importance of science education in any society cannot be overemphasized that is why any society that aspires to be great must pay adequate attention to the quality of science education. Science education is taught in most senior secondary schools in Nigeria as Biology, Physics and Chemistry respectively. Chemistry is one of the core science subjects' students are expected to pass before being admitted into higher institutions of learning in Nigeria to pursue science - based programs such as Medicine, Pharmacy, Engineering, Agriculture and Biochemistry (Bolaji, 2017). Despite the importance of Chemistry, West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) annual reports has shown that there is a decline in chemistry achievement over the years, which revealed failure rate increasing from 27.28% to 77.99% while the pass rate decreases from 50.95% to 10.00% respectively. Research findings show that students perform poorly on the concept Electrolysis (Adeoye, 2016 and Ifeanyi, 2017). Some research findings attributed students' poor achievement in Chemistry to lack of adequate mastery of chemistry content knowledge by teachers in some selected areas in Chemistry (Agu, and Odu, 2016). This implies that some chemistry teachers are not well - versed and competent enough in teaching some aspects of Chemistry. Moreover, Okeke (2015) and (Odogu and Oduguisi, 2017) attributed the cause of students' poor achievement in chemistry to interest. This implies that students' interest in the learning of chemistry may negatively influence the quality of learning outcome thereby lowering achievement. Some research findings also attributed the causes of poor achievement in Chemistry to students' ability levels (Agu and Odu, 2016). This may be connected to students' entry behavior or levels of exposure resulting to being low, medium or high ability levels respectively. This implies that, students within the low and medium ability levels may be at disadvantaged, therefore, the need to bridge the existing gap between the levels becomes necessary, as findings revealed divergent opinions (Okeke, 2015) and (Adai and Bayo, 2017). However, traditional methods of instruction have been the most commonly used instructional strategies in most Nigerian secondary schools and have been found to be inadequate for chemistry instruction (Okeke, 2015). Nevertheless, innovative teaching strategies such as team teaching and collaborative strategies are being employed to mitigate the inadequacies of these traditional methods.

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Team teaching is an instructional strategy involving groups of teachers working together in a well-structured platform for effective classroom delivery (Adai and Bayo, 2017). Collaborative teaching strategy involves students working together as a team by sharing ideas during problem solving with, little guide from the teacher (Okeke, 2015). Collaborative strategies among others includes Think Pare – Share, Three – step interview, Jigsaw (II) and Students Teams – Achievement Division (STAD). Thus, this research intends to investigate the effects of collaborative and team teaching strategies on achievement, ability levels and interesting Chemistry among senior secondary school students in Kwara state. Despite the importance of Chemistry, the WAEC chief examiners annual reports revealed a continued decline in Chemistry achievement as shown in Table 1 which revealed that from 2012 - 2018 failure rate increases from 27.28% to 77.99% while the pass rate decreases from 50.95% to 10.00% respectively.

Table1: May /June, 2012 – 2018, West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) Results.

Year	Total Sat	Total Credit A1 – C6	Total Pass D7 – E8	Total Fail F9
2012	349,936	178,274 (50.95%)	66,423 (18.71%)	47,913 (27.28%)
2013	380,140	170,670 (44.50%)	86,423 (22.73%)	11,448 (30.11%)
2014	391,160	165,265 (42.25%)	74,751 (19.11%)	151,144 (38.64%)
2015	401,723	178,164 (34.35%)	93,642 (23.31%)	129,917 (42.34%)
2016	403,528	158,465 (34.27%)	94,990 (23.54%)	150,072 (47.19%)
2017	411,356	150,145 (25.20%)	91,444 (15.80%)	169,766 (60.90%)
2018	464,853	46,488 (10.00%)	55,780 (11.99%)	362,585 (77.99%)

Source: WAEC Headquarter Yaba, Lagos state (September, 2018)

Also chemistry students do not perform well in the concept of Chemical reactions (Bolaji, 2017). Research findings attributed students' poor achievement in chemical reaction to the use of poor and inadequate instructional strategies (Odogwu and Oduguisi, 2017), lack of adequate mastery of chemical reactions by teachers (Agu, and Odu, 2016), lack of adequate interest to learning of chemical reactions or related problems among chemistry students (Okeke, 2015) and variations gender among students in chemistry achievement (Agu and Odu, 2016). However, traditional methods of instruction have been the most commonly used instructional strategies in most Nigerian secondary schools and have been found to be inadequate for chemistry instruction. Therefore, the need to seek for alternative teaching strategies becomes necessary. That is why the researcher intends to investigate the effects of jig - saw and team teaching learning strategies on chemistry achievement and retention among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government, Kwara state.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to determine the effects of:

1. Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on achievement in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.
2. Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on retention in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.

Research Question

The study will attempt to provide answers to the following research questions;

1. What are the effects of Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on achievement in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin government?
2. What are the effects of Jig-Saw and Team-teaching instructional strategies on retention in Chemical reactions among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government?

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level.

1. There is no significant difference between achievement of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team –Teaching strategy among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.
2. There is no significant difference between retention of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team –Teaching strategy among senior secondary school students in Ilorin west local government.

Methodology

Quasi experimental research design, specifically, Pretest Posttest non randomized nonequivalent control group design. The population of the study consists 1620 (1124 male & 496 female) Class II Chemistry students. Sample size of 210 (117 male & 93 female) class II Chemistry students using an intact class of 3 out of 10 secondary schools randomly selected by lottery technique in Ilorin west local government area of kwara state were used for the study as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Sampled SSII Students in Ilorin West LGA

School	Group	Male	Female	Total
G.D.S.S, Air Port	Jig-Saw	45	29	79
L.G.S.S Osin Aremu	Team Teaching	49	40	89
Ilorin Grammar Sch. Ilorin	Control	23	24	47
	Total	117	93	210

Chemistry Students Achievement Test (CSAT), the CSAT was developed using blooms taxonomy of learning which covers the entire 4 sub - topics on the concept chemical kinetics as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Table of Specifications for Chemistry Students Achievement Test

Content Area	Remember	Understand	Apply	Analyze	Evaluate	Create	Total
Types of Reaction	13	11, 12	16	20	-	-	5
Chemical Kinetics	1, 14, 25	23	9	-	2	-	6
Factors affecting Reaction Rate	3, 5, 7	17	19, 24	21	6	-	8
Calculations /Theories	15	4	8	18	-	10, 22	6
Total Items	8	5	5	3	2	2	25

Source: Anderson and Krathworl in Bidemi, (2017).

The CSAT and marking schemes were validated by three experts from University of Ilorin, Ilorin Kwara State. The CSAT was pilot tested using an intact class of 63 class two 2018/19 Chemistry students from Omu Aran High School, Omu Aran, Kwara State. The same instrument was applied to the same group of students after an interval of two weeks (test-retest method). The reliability coefficient of 0.933 was gotten for CSAT using Guttman's Split half Correlation Coefficient reliability test. The CSAT was administered to the students in a normal class room setting for pretest scores. Experimental groups were taught the concept chemical kinetics using jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategies, respectively while control group were taught using lecture method. A reshuffled version of the CSAT was then administered to the students to measure achievement. 2 weeks later, the CSAT was re - reshuffled and administered to the students as post – posttest to measure students' retention in chemical kinetics. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions raised, analysis of variance (ANOVA) to analyze if pretest result was significant or not. Thus, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The statistical package for social sciences (version 23.0) was used to analyze data. Thus, the research lasted for six (6) weeks.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean achievement scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students achievement in Chemistry

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Jig-Saw	74	27.45	3.12	42.04	4.61	14.59
Team teaching	89	25.82	3.87	42.76	4.17	16.94

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Control	47	24.12	4.92	26.38	6.35	2.26
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Table 5, revealed a pretest result for jig-saw group having a mean achievement score of 27.45 with standard deviation of 3.12, while posttest result shows a mean score of 42.04 with standard deviation score of 4.61. Hence, had a mean gain score of 14.59. Similarly, pretest result for team teaching group revealed a mean achievement score of 25.82 with standard deviation of 3.87, while posttest result gave a mean score of 42.76 with standard deviation score of 4.17. Hence, had a mean gain score of 16.94, the control group pretest results revealed mean achievement score of 24.12 with standard deviation of 4.92, while posttest result gave mean achievement score of 26.38 with standard deviation of 6.35. Hence, mean gain of 2.263. These, results revealed that both jig-saw and team teaching had higher mean achievement score than control group, but team-teaching group had higher mean gain than jig - saw group. Thus, to find out how significant the difference was, analysis of covariance ANCOVA was used to test the null hypothesis from research question 1 raised as shown in table 7.

Research Question 2

What is the mean retention scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area?

Table 6: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students Retention Rate in Chemistry

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Jig-saw	74	42.04	4.61	55.27	2.37	13.32
Team teaching	89	42.76	4.17	58.18	2.53	15.42
Control	47	26.38	6.35	31.15	2.47	4.778

Table 6, revealed a pretest result for jig-saw group having a mean score of 42.04 with standard deviation of 4.61, while posttest result shows a mean score of 55.27 with standard deviation score of 2.37, had a mean gain score of 13.32. Similarly, pretest result for team teaching group revealed a mean score of 42.76 with standard deviation of 4.17, while posttest result gave a mean score of 58.18 with standard deviation score of 2.53, had a mean gain score of 35.42. The control group pretest results revealed mean achievement score of 26.38 with standard deviation of 6.35, while posttest result gave mean retention score of 31.15 with standard deviation of 2.47, had a mean gain score of 4.778. These, results revealed that both jig-saw and team-teaching strategy had higher retention score than control group, but team-teaching groups had higher mean gain score on retention than jigsaw groups. Thus, to find out how significant the difference was, analysis of covariance ANCOVA was used to test the null hypothesis from research question 2 raised as shown in table 8.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team- Teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area.

Table 7: Summary of ANCOVA Test Results of Groups with Achievement

Source	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F _{cal}	P value
Corrected Model	9958.241 ^a	3	3319.414	14.685	0.000
Intercept	28667.327	1	28667.327	126.821	0.000
pretest	536.457	1	536.457	2.373	0.125
Group	8248.057	2	4121.028	18.244	0.000
Error	46565.573	206	226.046		
Total	373365.000	210			
Corrected total	56523.814	209			

Significant at P > 0.000

Table 7 revealed that $F_{(2, 206)} = 18.244$ and $P = 0.000$ at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that p value is less than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) which is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis one was rejected. There is significant

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difference between jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy on senior secondary school student's achievement in the concept chemical kinetics.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught chemical reaction using Jig-Saw strategy and those exposed to Team- Teaching strategy in Ilorin west Local government area?

Table 8: Summary of ANCOVA Test Results of Groups with Retention

Source	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F _{cal}	P _{value}
Corrected Model	36452.765 ^a	3	12150.92	245.976	0.000
Intercept	46541.824	1	46541.82	176.104	0.000
Pretest	162.211	1	162.211	0.614	0.434
Group	34294.971	2	17147.48	64.882	0.000
Error	54442.992	206	264.286		
Total	566991.000	210			
Corrected total	90895.757	209			

Significant at P < 0.05

Table 8 revealed that $F_{(2, 206)} = 64.882$ and $P = 0.000$ at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that p value is less than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) which is significant. Therefore, null hypothesis two was rejected. This means that there is significant difference between jig-saw and team-teaching strategies on senior secondary school student's retention in the concept chemical reaction.

Discussion of Finding

The findings of this study revealed that there is significant difference between achievement of students taught the concept chemical reaction using Jig-Saw instructional strategy and those expose to lecture Team-teaching strategy. The finding is in agreement with the findings of Okeke (2015), Odogu and Oduguisi (2017) which revealed significant difference jigsaw instructional strategy and achievement in concept chemical reaction among secondary school students.

Conclusion

Jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy improves secondary school students' achievement and retention in Chemistry.

Recommendations

Based on research findings for this study, it was recommended that:

1. Jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy should be adequately used frequently by teachers during Chemistry instructions to aid better achievement in Chemistry among secondary school students.
2. Jig-saw and team-teaching instructional strategy should be adequately used frequently by teachers during Chemistry instructions to aid better retention in Chemistry among secondary school students.

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